

1 *Original Article*2 **Informed consent: a review of the practice in a developing country.**3 **Bashiru Aminu¹, Makama Jerry Godfrey¹, Mukoro Duke George^{2*}**4 1Division of General Surgery,
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14 * Correspondence: doplass@yahoo.com ; Tel.: +2348069432297 (Bashir Aminu)15 **Abstract:**16 *Background*17 *Informed consent is a legal document reflecting the assurance of the patient that the surgeon, at all times: "in disease, focuses on*
18 *two aims, to improve and not to cause damage is aimed at the lawfulness of health assistance. It therefore influences the medical*
19 *profession's everyday activities.*20 *The situation of informed consent in developing countries and resource-constrained health centers may be deteriorating evidenced*
21 *by the increase in legal battles and improvement in patients' awareness of his/her right to comprehensive informed health care*
22 *which may be influenced by information from the internet.*23 *Objective*24 *Evaluate the quality of informed consent practice and documentation. Also, evaluate the perception and knowledge among doctors*
25 *in their current state, identify ethical gaps, and discuss the current legal implications.*26 *Methods*27 **Citation:** Authors First and Initials

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40*A survey was carried out among healthcare workers in Nigeria between January 2023 and June 2023 using a structured questionnaire to ascertain their perception and practice of informed consent.**Results**Among 122 doctors who participated in the survey. 79 (64.8%) were consultants, and 90 (73.8%) worked for over 10 years. Among them, 110 (90.2 %) believed the lowest cadre (house officer) should ensure that valid consent is taken. Most forms 99 (81.1%) are usually generalized and non-specific with only 17 (13.9%) having the name of the procedure in print while Only 40 (32.8%) of the consent forms had details of the surgery. Only 44 (36.1%) listed common major risks. 106 (86.9%) of the consent forms were less than 2 pages. 70 (57.4 %) stated that their consent forms were very similar to other institutions, 88 (72.1%) documented the competency of the patient, and Only 18 (14.8%) contained alternative treatment. 5.7% had translation in the local dialect 76 (62.3%) believed the quality of information given was what a reasonable body of doctors should expect. In comparison, only 46 (37.7%) indicated the information is what a*

41 *reasonable patient would expect. About 15 (12.3%) participants knew the Bolam test while only 31 (25.4%) knew the*
42 *Montgomery test. The study revealed that elements of informed consent were of variable deficiency in practice among healthcare*
43 *workers.*

44 *Conclusion*

45 *There is a need for the training of doctors and developing a specific document used for obtaining uniform and standard informed*
46 *consent from patients. The study reflects the need for recurring audits of practice among healthcare workers to prevent legal*
47 *backlash or fallout.*

48 *Keywords; Informed consent, medical ethics, healthcare, legal*

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51 **1. Introduction**

52 Informed consent is a legal document reflecting the assurance of the patient that the surgeon, at all times: "in disease,
53 focuses on two aims, to improve and not to cause damage and is aimed at the lawfulness of health assistance¹⁻². It
54 therefore influences the medical profession's everyday activities. It predates Egyptian and Greek civilizations and is
55 not a new concept."¹⁻² Its importance, therefore, cannot be overemphasized. The consent process and consent forms
56 in Nigeria have not been optimal.² While the Code of Medical Ethics in Nigeria, Rule 19 of part A which deals with
57 informed consent, guides the conduct of physicians,^{3,4} there are no government guidelines to follow on the standard
58 consent form.² Even in the absence of laid down procedures, hospitals have not taken the time to develop consent
59 forms, to meet with the rapidly changing times and, in some cases, have resorted to copying one another.²

60 In a U.S. court case in 1914, it was stated that it is the right of an adult with the capability to make decisions
61 concerning his own body and that any surgical operation without the patient's consent is considered an assault⁵. In
62 another U.S. court case, the court stated that a doctor must make a reasonable disclosure to his patient of the nature,
63 probable consequences, and dangers of the proposed treatment to the patient⁵ The consent form should therefore
64 contain a minimum of the following required elements for documentation of the informed consent discussion⁶ : (1)
65 the nature of the procedure, (2) the risks and benefits of the procedure, (3) reasonable alternatives, (4) risks and
66 benefits of alternatives, and (5) assessment of the patient's understanding of elements 1 through 46. These are
67 important criteria and are frequently absent in many forms.²

68 Current guidance states that the person obtaining consent must either (1) be capable of performing the procedure
69 themselves; or (2) have received specialist training in advising patients about the procedure⁷, but in some cases, the
70 forms are supervised by nurses⁸. The state determines the required standard for informed consent. The three
71 acceptable legal approaches to assessing the adequacy of informed consent are (1) Subjective standard: What would
72 this patient need to know and understand to make an informed decision? (2) Reasonable patient standard What
73 would the average patient need to know to be an informed participant in the decision? (3) Reasonable physician
74 standard: What would a typical physician say about this procedure?⁶ Many countries now appear to lean toward the
75 use of the "reasonable patient standard" because it focuses on what a typical patient needs to know to understand the
76 decision^{6,9-11}It is the sole obligation of the provider to determine which approach is appropriate for a given
77 situation^{6,9-11} Trouble usually arises when medical negligence occurs.

78 While noting that the surgeon owes a medical duty of care to his patient,¹²⁻¹⁴ a duty of care is an obligation on a
79 party to take care not to allow an injury to be suffered by another individual¹²⁻¹⁴. Where a provider has failed to
80 meet the standard of conduct required of a reasonable provider under the same circumstances, his/ her behavior may

81 be called negligent¹²⁻¹⁴. Thus, Medical negligence is said to have occurred when a person in the medical profession
82 breaches his duty of care to a patient, resulting in actual injury to the patient¹²⁻¹⁴. It is an act or omission by a medical
83 practitioner during a patient's treatment that deviates from such accepted norms of medical practice in the medical
84 community. The preceding indicates a particular standard of care to assess the deviation from the norm.

85 Guidelines and evidence-based medicine are essential even though they should be adapted to the individual patient.
86 The validity of the informed consent taken by the surgeon comes into play here. A consent form not taken at all, not
87 appropriately handled, or does not capture risks adequately may lead to successful claims by a patient¹². A claim can
88 occur if, for example, a surgeon counsels a patient concerning common risks but fails to warn of a rare danger that
89 carries high morbidity and or mortality.^{12,15} This is known as the duty to warn cases^{12,15}. The Bolam principle
90 states that a doctor is not considered negligent if he acts by a practice accepted at the time by a responsible body of
91 medical opinion even though other doctors adopt a different practice.¹⁵ But this is not where it ends. The law does
92 not require medical professionals to be perfect every time they do their job; 100% perfection is not humanly possible.
93 The law requires that medical professionals exercise a reasonable standard of care for them¹⁶.

94 Courts in Australia and England have begun to display a paradigm shift by applying a stricter standard to the
95 information that doctors should give their patients—that of what a reasonable patient might expect rather than what a
96 good body of doctors might think¹⁶. It would appear that doctors in Nigeria have not yet caught up with this change
97 in judges' thinking and are thus laying themselves open to negligence claims¹⁶. Recourse is often made to ward round
98 notes without properly signed consent forms¹⁶. These have been rejected many times by the courts and appear not to
99 be equivalent to consent forms¹⁶. Nevertheless, well-documented notes still have their value¹⁶. Duty of care is
100 therefore a term which every surgeon must be conversant with but unfortunately, the legal definition of this term is
101 frequently not understood¹⁷ It is alarming that In the U.S., 7-17 malpractice claims are filed per 100 physicians every
102 year¹⁷⁻¹⁹. One of the things that is essential to know is how the legal system defines the standard of care and to what
103 standards we as physicians are being held¹⁷. If others in the business commonly practice a certain way that eliminates
104 hazards, then this practice can be used to define the standard of care.¹⁷ The courts are the final arbiters on whether
105 the practice is reasonable and whether the deviation is so unreasonable as to cause harm¹⁷.

106 In this study, we intend to review the current practice of informed consent, its adequacy or otherwise, and also
107 ascertain if the surgeon or physician is aware of the current paradigm shift from a reasonable surgeon/ physician
108 standard to that of a reasonable patient standard

109 Methodology

110 This is a cross-sectional descriptive study of medical doctors practicing in health institutions in the six geopolitical
111 zones in Nigeria using a structured self-administered questionnaire. No ethical approval was required from the Ethic
112 Committee of the Barau Dikko Teaching Hospital (BDTH), Kaduna State University, KASU. All medical doctors
113 working at any departments of health institutions in the six geopolitical zones in Nigeria were included.

114 It was conducted using a well-structured questionnaire to evaluate the following areas of the informed consent: (1) the
115 nature of the procedure, (2) the risks and benefits of the procedure, (3) reasonable alternatives, (4) risks and benefits of
116 alternatives, and (5) assessment of the patient's understanding of elements 1 through 4. The three acceptable legal
117 approaches to assessing the adequacy of informed consent were also evaluated. Basic demographics of the
118 participants including location of practice, years of practice, qualifications, and designation were included in the
119 evaluation. Data was entered into SPSS Version 22.0 statistical software and results were presented as simple
120 frequencies and percentages.

121 Results

One hundred and twenty-two doctors participated in the survey spanning the six geopolitical zones, all specialties, and qualifications. Seventy-nine (64.8%) were consultants, 3 (2.5%), were medical officers, 17(13.9%) were senior registrars, 13 (10.7%) were registrars, and 10 (8.2%) were house officers. Figure 1. 90 (73.8%) worked for more than 10 years, 14 (11.5%) were obstetricians and gynecologists, 4 (3.3%) internal medicine, 10 (8.2%) laboratory medicine. 11 (9.0%) were psychiatrists, 12 (9.8%) had worked for 5-10 years, 20 (16.4%) less than 5 years. Fifty (41%) were surgeons, 1(9.0%) were pediatricians, 11 (9.0%) were radiologists and 11 (9.0%), were family medicine. About 110 (90.2 %) believed that a house officer should ensure that valid consent is taken, while 12 (9.8%) stated that the person performing the procedure should take the consent. 108 (88.5%) indicated that the perioperative nurse usually detected unsigned consent forms, while 14 (11.5%) indicated that the managing team detected unsigned consent forms.

Ninety-nine (81.1%) indicated no procedure-specific consent form while only 23 (18.9%) indicated that each procedure had a specific consent form. One hundred (82%), took consent on the day of surgery just before surgery while 22 (18%) took consent in the clinic before admission. One hundred and five (86.1%) did not have a structured consent form with the name of the procedure in print but was handwritten before surgery and readjusted after surgery. in contrast, 17 (13.9%) had the name of the procedure in print. Only 40 (32.8%) of the consent forms had an explanation of the details of the surgery while 82 (67.2%) did not. Only 44 (36.1%) of consent forms listed common risks majorly, while 78 (63.9%) did not list any. 100 (82.0%) did not list uncommon risks, and only 22 (18.0%) listed a few but not all uncommon ones. 106 (86.9%) of the consent forms were less than 2 pages, 9 (7.4%) between 2-3 pages, 3 (2.5%) between 3-5 pages, and 4 (3.3%) were more than 5 pages. seventy (57.4 %) stated that their consent forms were similar to other institutions, and 52 (42.6%) had different forms. 88 (72.1%) indicated that their forms stated the competency of the patient, while 34 (27.9%) did not.

Only 18 (14.8%) contained alternative treatment while about 104 (85.2%) did not. About 7 ((5.7%) had translation in the local dialect but 115 (85.2%) did not. About 108 (88.5%) did not clearly state the risk of not undergoing treatment but in 14 (11.5%) of cases, this information was found. In 102 (83.6%) of cases, the chances of success were not stated at all, only 20 (16.4%) indicated some measure of success. In 76 (62.3%) of cases, the quality of information given was that of a reasonable surgeon, 46 (37.7%) however indicated that of a reasonable patient. Figure 2. About 15 (12.3%) knew the Bolam test but 107 (87.7%) did not. Figure 3. 91 (74.6%) of respondents had not heard of the Montgomery test, and only 31 (25.4%) were aware of it Figure 4. In about 36 (70.5%) of cases, the consent did not contain answers to commonly asked questions, 36 (29.5%) however attempted to answer some few questions, and 60% of these were found in the southeast and southwestern zones

Figure 1. Designation of respondents

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Figure 2 Quality of information given

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Figure 3. Respondent knows the Bolam test

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Figure 4. Respondent knows Montgomery test

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164 **Discussion**

165 It is not uncommon in our environment to encounter patients who have had surgery in the past but are not able to
166 give an idea of what was done to them. The informed consent if properly handled should curb this²⁰. Most of the
167 participants (64.8%) were specialists who were trainers in the art of consent-taking, or trainees being taught the art of

168 informed consent and had spent more than 10 years (73.8%) in practice. With over 41% who were surgeons, 11.5%
169 obstetricians and gynecologists, and the rest who were physicians from various specializations performing one
170 procedure or other requiring an informed consent there was a reasonable exposure to consent taking. Kidmas et al²⁰,
171 found that the degree of awareness of the patient was related to the grade of the surgeon performing the consent-
172 taking and booking of the patient.

173 Current guidelines state that the person obtaining consent must either (1) be capable of performing the procedure
174 themselves; or (2) have received specialist training in advising patients about the procedure,⁷ however in this study it
175 was found that about 90.2 % believed that a house officer should take consent, while only 9.8% stated that the person
176 performing the procedure should take the consent. This large number may indicate high patient turnover centers with
177 limited qualified staff but it is in exactly situations such as this that errors are fraught to occur. According to Kidmas
178 et al²⁰, for consent to be valid, three conditions must be satisfied: the patient must be competent, must have sufficient
179 information to make an informed choice and the consent must be given voluntarily. These judgments may be
180 occasionally difficult for the intern to make. Probably because it is left in the purview of the house officer, 88.5% of
181 unsigned forms were usually detected by the perioperative nurse, while only 11.5% indicated that other more senior
182 members of the managing team detected unsigned consent forms this leaves a big window for malpractice claims
183 since a procedure without valid consent is considered as an assault^{5,20-21} Ezeome et al⁴ found Instances where major
184 elective surgeries have been done without consent. In 82% of cases, these consents were taken on the day of surgery
185 by the intern and, as found in the study by Kidmas et al²⁰, these patients hardly remembered what they were told
186 afterward. Agu et al²² also found that despite training on informed consent most surgeons still relied on nurses to get
187 informed consent from their patients²².

188 The Code of Medical Ethics in Nigeria stipulates a standard structure for the consent form^{2,6,17-19}. This study
189 found that most of the forms were single-paged, scanty, and similar to one another. Ezeome et al² found similar
190 findings and in some instances, some institutions appeared to have copied one another. Pierre OO et al²⁸ made
191 similar findings. The more detailed forms were found in the southwest and southeastern parts of the country in this
192 study, probably due to higher literacy rates, litigation, or both.

193 The more the patient asks about the procedure the more he/she should be informed, since questioning implies a
194 desire to be fully informed²⁰. In this study it was found that 67.2% did not explain the details of their surgery, 63.9%
195 did not mention common risks and almost no mention (82%) of the uncommon risks were made. Neither was the risk
196 of no treatment nor the chances of success (88.5% and 88.3% respectively) discussed. This was more common in the
197 northern region probably because of a lower literacy rate or a reluctance by patients to know more or both²⁰
198 compared to other regions. These patients would probably require more information as shown by Agu et al²⁷ in a
199 study in which more than 75% of all the respondents irrespective of educational status wanted to be involved in
200 decisions about their healthcare and more than half wanted full disclosure of information. More information was
201 required in the findings by Osime in the south-south, and a study in the southwestern regions by Aisuodionoe-
202 Shadrach et al²³. In the southeastern regions, however, a study by Agu et al²² showed a varying picture. While some
203 doctors rely on nurses to get their consent forms signed, in most cases, motivation to get consent arises when surgeons
204 are dealing with educated/enlightened patients, there is a high risk of complications, or the surgeon is worried about
205 malpractice litigation. In these situations, greater detail was discussed. Language was observed to be a big barrier in
206 this study as also noted by Ezeome et al² and Osime et al²⁵ in their studies where it appeared to be related to
207 educational level.

208 The court as earlier alluded, is the final arbiter in cases of negligence. The information required during informed
209 consent may be either of the following three acceptable legal approaches (1) Subjective standard: What would this

210 patient need to know and understand to make an informed decision? (2) Reasonable patient standard What would the
211 average patient need to know to be an informed participant in the decision? (3) Reasonable physician standard: What
212 would a typical physician say about this procedure?⁶ Many countries as mentioned earlier, now appear to lean
213 toward the use of the "reasonable patient standard" because it focuses on what a typical patient needs to know to
214 understand the decision^{6,9-11} In this study 62.3% preferred the `reasonable physician standard` and were not aware
215 of the Bolam test (87%) or Montgomery test (74.6%). In 1957, the Bolam test stipulated that no doctor could be guilty
216 of negligence if his actions were acceptable by a responsible body of knowledge^{6,9-11}. The Bolitho test helped clarify
217 any ambiguity by defining a `responsible body` as one whose opinion had a logical basis, in the case of Bolam it was a
218 responsible body of doctors^{6,9-14}. The Montgomery test however is a paradigm shift requiring that a doctor inform
219 the patient of all risks that a reasonable patient in that condition requires, in other words, all that he or she must or
220 needs to know.^{6,9-14} It is worthwhile to note that Agu et al ²⁷ in their study reported that more than half of patients
221 wanted full disclosure. In this study it was found that these doctors were not aware of these, nor the paradigm shift
222 in the thinking of the courts, thus exposing themselves to litigation. This occurs commonly where it appears there is a
223 general lack of consensus as to what risks in a particular operation are significant to discuss leading to variation in the
224 information and explanation given²³ Aisuodionoe-Shedrac et al found the variation in the information given to be
225 greater whenever the trainees take consent, as a result of variation within grades and between grades.

226 **Conclusion**

227 Informed consent as currently practiced is suboptimal.

228 There is a need for more awareness to improve the quality of information given to patients, documentation, and the
229 mode of obtaining informed consent.

230 The outcome of the surgical procedure may be unfavorable but properly taken informed consent may prevent
231 litigation.

232 Doctors should be aware of the paradigm shift in the thought process of the legal courts.

233 **Recommendations**

234 Another national study to evaluate the responses of patients concerning the quality of consent obtained from doctors
235 may be required.

236 A larger more all-inclusive study of doctors' practice on informed consent in Nigeria may aid in policy formulation.

237 A complete review of the consent process and consent forms in Nigeria is necessary.

238 Conflict of interest None

239 Ethical clearance None required

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